

TABLE 2

Compound	Wavelength m μ	Bands kK	Molar extinction	Assignments
BipyH ₂ [CrOCl ₂]	720	13.89	100	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	590	16.94	190	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	460	21.74	580	³ B ₂ → ³ A ₁
				(xy → z ²)
	420	23.81	860	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	300	33.34	11500	π → π^*
PhenH ₂ [CrOCl ₂]	236	42.37	11800	(transition in bipyH ₂ ²⁺) ³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
	690	14.50	135	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	540	18.52	306	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	430	23.26	644	³ B ₂ → ³ A ₁
	335	29.85	7200	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	268	37.32	10120	π → π^*
				(transition in phenH ₂ ²⁺)
[CrOCl ₂ .bipy]	700	14.29	170	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	590	16.90	280	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	465	21.50	400	a ₂ (xy) → a ₁ (x ² -y ²)
	395	25.31	1050	a ₂ → a ₁ (z ²)
	278	35.97	16102	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]
	238	42.02	13900	π → π^*
				(in bipy)
[CrOCl ₂ .phen]	680	14.71	120	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	530	18.87	448	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	416	24.00	808	a ₂ → a ₁ [*]
	325	30.77	7360	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]
	246	40.46	12160	π → π^*
			(in phen)	
[CrOCl ₂ .Cpy]	750	13.33	50.0	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	600	16.69	148.80	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	450	22.22	421.40	b ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	395	25.31	562.0	a ₂ → a ₁ [*]
				(xy → x ² -y ²)
	310	32.25	5082	a ₂ → a ₁ [*] (z ²)
	250	40.00	8677	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]

phase in Perkin Elmer 621 spectrophotometer to locate different stretching bands, mainly Cr(V)=O stretching band. This band appears in all the compounds in the region 930-955 cm⁻¹ as has been observed previously in identical cases⁷⁻⁹. Electronic transition spectra both in the ultraviolet and visible regions were taken in Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer in acetonitrile and bands with probable assignments are given in Table 2. The assignments of bands are based on the work of McGlynn, Garner and Selbin on similar compounds^{9,10}. First derivative of esr absorption spectra of the powdered compounds were recorded in Alpha EPR spectrophotometer. The average <g> values were calculated (Table 1) which also support the paramagnetism corresponding to one unpaired electron.

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References

1. R. F. WEINLAND and W. FRIDRICH, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3784.
2. R. F. WEINLAND and M. FRIEDERER, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4042.
3. R. F. WEINLAND and M. FRIEDERER, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2090.

4. O. V. ZIEBARTH and J. SELBIN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 849.
5. H. KON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, 25, 933.
6. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 110.
7. H. B. GRAY and C. R. HARE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 363
8. C. J. BARRACLOUGH, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.
9. C. D. GARNER, J. KENDRICK, P. LAMBERT, F. E. MABBS and I. H. HILLIER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 1287.
10. L. G. VANQUICKENBORNE and S. P. MCGLYNN, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 2, 393.

Molecular Adducts of Diphenyltin Diisothiocyanate with Some Nitrogen and Oxygen Donors*

(Mrs.) RAJESHWARI RUPAINWAR and B. D. PANDEY*
Chemistry Section, Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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THE synthesis and structural studies of diphenyltin dihalide complexes have been undertaken by certain research groups during the last fifteen years but only a few complexes of diphenyltin

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*Applied Chemistry Section, I.T., B.H.U., Varanasi.

dipseudothalides are known. Holloway and coworkers¹ have reported the acceptor properties of triphenyltin isothiocyanate with some N- and O-donor ligands and also a few diphenyltin diisothiocyanate adducts of 1:1 or 1:2 stoichiometry. Srivastava and Agarwal² have reported the complexes of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ with bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline. Recently, Srivastava and Kamboj³ have prepared and characterised a number of adducts of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ with various ligands. The present communication describes the adducts of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ with several N- and O-donors having 1:1 stoichiometry with monodentate ligands and also a few 1:2 compounds.

Experimental

$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ was prepared from Ph_2SnCl_2 and potassium thiocyanate in acetone. The product was recrystallised from benzene and characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectrum, (m.p. 178°). As the starting compound was somewhat unstable and susceptible to moisture, it was immediately used under dry conditions.

The ligands were of AnalaR/G.R. grade and were used without further purification. The abbreviations used in the text are TMA (trimethylamine), TEA (triethylamine), TPA (triphenylamine), DPF (diphenyl formamide), DMA (dimethyl acetamide), DPA (diphenyl acetamide), DMO (dimethyl oxamide), Apy (antipyrine), DPSO (diphenyl sulphoxide), DBSO (dibenzyl sulphoxide) and IqO (isoquinoline-N-oxide).

Preparation of the adducts: The complexes were prepared by the interaction of the solutions in acetone, of the reactants (5 m mole each) taken in 1:1 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed for 1 or 2 hr. Excess of the solvent was distilled off followed by precipitation with either diethyl ether

(method A) or petroleum ether (method B). The crude product was separated by filtration, recrystallised with either of the solvents and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in freezing nitrobenzene. Conductance of the compounds was measured in nitrobenzene at a single dilution of $10^{-4}M$ with Philips PR-950J conductivity bridge using a dip type conductivity cell. The infrared spectra, in KBr discs or nujol, were recorded with Perkin Elmer 621 spectrometer. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1 and the relevant ir bands in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The adducts I-VIII analyse correctly to 1:1 $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ and ligand ratio, while the compounds IX-XI are 1:2 complexes. All the compounds are white crystalline solids, soluble in common organic solvents. The adducts are slightly sensitive to moisture on continuous exposure.

The significantly lower observed values of the molecular weights from the calculated values may be attributed to substantial dissociation on dissolution of the adducts in nitrobenzene. The conductance values reveal essentially nonionic nature.

The ir spectra of the adducts were recorded in the region $4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and in a few representative cases even upto 200 cm^{-1} . A band at 2085 cm^{-1} in the free Lewis acid assigned to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ shows a negative shift of $25-45\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the adducts (Table 2). The $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{C}-\text{N})$ of the free trimethylamine, observed⁴ at 1043 cm^{-1} , has been identified at 984 cm^{-1} in the complex. Similar negative shifts of the (C-N) asymmetric absorptions in TEA and TPA complexes are also observed, though the bands are split (Table 2). This indicates electron pair

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ COMPLEXES

Compound	Method	m.p. °C	M. Wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Sp. Cond. $\times 10^7$	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	Sn
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, TMA (I)	A	130d	350 (448)	3.4	45.1 (45.5)	4.6 (4.4)	27.0 (26.3)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, TEA (II)	A	77-79	399 (490)	2.4	49.2 (48.9)	4.9 (5.1)	25.0 (24.2)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, TPA (III)	B	145	550 (634)	2.3	61.2 (60.5)	3.9 (3.4)	19.5 (18.7)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DPF (IV)	B	101	470 (586)	1.9	53.9 (55.2)	3.4 (3.5)	20.8 (20.3)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DMA (V)	A	105	304 (476)	2.9	44.8 (45.3)	3.7 (3.9)	24.4 (25.0)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DPA (VI)	B	109	485 (600)	2.9	55.4 (56.0)	4.0 (3.8)	20.0 (19.8)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DMO (VII)	B	130-32	400 (505)	2.8	43.2 (42.7)	4.0 (3.5)	24.2 (23.5)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, Apy (VIII)	B	143	483 (577)	2.4	51.6 (51.9)	3.6 (3.8)	20.2 (20.6)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, 2DPSO (IX)	B	118	563 (793)	2.8	58.0 (57.5)	3.9 (3.7)	15.4 (15.0)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, 2DBSO (X)	B	97-98	612 (849)	2.9	60.0 (59.3)	4.8 (4.4)	14.9 (14.0)
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, 2IqO (XI)	B	142	491 (647)	2.6	59.0 (58.7)	4.0 (3.7)	19.0 (18.3)

TABLE 2—RELEVANT IR BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF THE $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$ COMPLEXES

Compound	$\nu_{\text{asym.}}(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{E}=\text{O})$ E = C, N or S	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\Delta\nu(\text{E}=\text{O})/(\text{C}-\text{N})$
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, TMA	2060 vs a(2005 vs) 2050 vs	—	984 m *(1043 s) 1130 s, 1064 s (1170 s)	59
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, TEA	2065 vs	—	1173 w, 1096 m (1190, 1085 m)	40
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, TPA	2065 vs	—	1274 s (1250 s)	17
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DPF	2065 vs	1647 vs (1685 vs)	1270 m (1265 s)	34
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DMA	2065 vs	1608 vs (1633 vs)	1363 m (1320 s)	25
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DPA	2060 vs	1600 vs, 1590 vs (1678 vs)	1245 s (1240 s)	78
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, DMO	2060 vs	1650 vs (1685 s)	—	35
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, Apy	2060 vs, 2040 vs	1562 s, 1550 m (1666 m)	—	104
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, 2DPSO	2040 vs	964, 934 vs (1046 s)	—	82
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, 2DBSO	2060 vs, 2038 sh	987, 980 s, 940 sh (1036 vs)	—	49
$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2$, 2IqO	2048 vs	1155 m (1180 s)	—	25

* Values in parenthesis correspond to pure ligand bands.
a band corresponding to free Lewis acid.

s = strong, vs = very strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder, w = weak.

donation from the nitrogen atom of the amine to the tin, and TMA being the most firmly bound while TPA the least.

In the amide complexes, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of the free ligand undergoes a profound negative shift (Table 2) of 25-78 cm^{-1} on complexation, thereby indicating the bonding of oxygen to the metal⁵. A positive shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ contiguous to the carbonyl group further substantiates that the amides act as monodentate ligands bonding through O atom and not the N atom of the ligands. However, the DMO acts as a bidentate ligand attached through both the oxygen atoms as the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at 1685 cm^{-1} appears at 1650 cm^{-1} in the adduct having no absorption due to uncoordinated C=O group; also $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ of the ligand does not show any change on complexation.

The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of the free antipyrine located at 1666 cm^{-1} registers a negative shift of 104 cm^{-1} in the adduct suggesting monodentate behaviour of the ligand⁶.

An absorption at 1046 cm^{-1} in the uncomplexed DPSO appeared as a split band at 964 and 934 cm^{-1} in its adduct which unequivocally refers to the bonding from O atom of the ligand⁷. A similar negative shift of 45 cm^{-1} was also noticed for the DBSO complex and the extent of this shift is often taken as the comparative donor ability⁸ of the sulphoxides DPSO, DBSO. A strong band at 1180 cm^{-1} of the IqO was found at 1155 cm^{-1} in its adduct. In addition, $\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$ of the free IqO, identified at 825 cm^{-1} , yields a vibration at 810 cm^{-1} on complexation showing coordination⁹ from

the oxygen atom. The bonding of the O atom of the ligands to the metal in these derivatives may be further indicated by the appearance of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ in the range 390-340 cm^{-1} . However, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ for the amine complexes were identified in the range 480-410 cm^{-1} .

On the basis of foregoing discussions, it may be concluded that the 1:1 adducts are probably pentacoordinated, while the 1:1 DMO complex and the 1:2 derivatives are hexacoordinated.

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References

1. J. H. HOLLOWAY, G. P. MCQUILAN and D. S. ROSS, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1971, 1935.
2. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and M. P. AGARWAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 3416.
3. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and V. P. KAMBOJ, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 857.
4. G. G. GILBAUT and S. M. BILLEDEAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 1167.
5. G. MATSUBAYASHI, T. TANAKA and R. OKOWARA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1968, 30, 1831.
6. D. N. SATYANARAYANA and C. C. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, 28, 2277.
7. W. KITCHING, C. J. MOORE and D. DODDRESS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 1149.
8. H. G. LANGER and A. H. BLUT, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 288.
9. J. H. NELSON, L. C. NATHAN and R. O. RAGSDALE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1840.